

The symbolism of the Flaming Sword in Freemasonry – Masonic poem about the Flaming Sword – Pictorial work

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Abstract

Swords are used in Freemasonry. More specifically, there is also the flaming sword that of the Brother Tyler, that of the Brother Expert, and that of the Brothers. What are they used for? What is the history of the sword?

What about the myth surrounding the flaming sword? In light of the Ancient and Accepted Scottish Rite and the modern Belgian Rite, this work attempts to highlight the importance of the use of the sword and its symbolism.

A poem about the flaming sword is included in this work.

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1. The sword in Freemasonry

First of all, we must distinguish between the different types of swords and their users.

There is the sword of the Worshipful Master, which has undulations and is called the “flaming sword.” Then there is the sword of the Tyler, which in many lodges is distinguished by its more imposing size, given that the Tyler is the guardian of the Temple. Then there is the sword of the Expert Brother, which can also be distinguished from the others in certain lodges. The Expert Brother is the only Brother who can walk around the Lodge without the intervention of the Master of Ceremonies. He will always carry his sword with him, for example, when he is dealing with the “Profane” (Laymen) who has knocked on the door of the Lodge. There are also the swords of the Brothers, which are generally all the same.

In Freemasonry, the sword is used at several points in the ritual. When we read the ritual of the Ancient and Accepted Scottish Rite, widely used in France, we can see its use at different points.

2. The flaming sword of the Worshipful Master

The flaming sword is used by the Worshipful Master. The Worshipful Master uses it especially to create, consecrate, and receive the Brother who has received the Light. He uses it for knighting. The flaming sword has an important symbolic value, representing the authority of the Worshipful Master and justice and impartiality. In this regard, we can recall the wisdom of King Solomon, who used his sword to render justice between two women who were quarrelling over the ownership of a baby.

Mackey's Masonic dictionary tells us that the flaming sword also recalls the sword carried by the cherubim who guarded the entrance to the tree of life in the Garden of Eden. Adam and Eve were expelled from the Garden of Eden because they had eaten the fruit forbidden by the Lord. Here is what we read in Genesis 3:24:

« After driving out the man, he placed cherubim and a flaming sword on the east side of the Garden of Eden to guard the way to the tree of life. »

3. The Sword of the Expert Brother

He will never leave his sword. He will use it at various points during the ritual, for example, to tile a Brother, to deal with the Profane. He may also use it to create a « Vault of Steel » with the Master of Ceremonies, who will use his staff.

The sword of the Brother Keeper, who stands in the West, at the door of the Lodge. Standing upright, he will hold his sword in front of him, pointing upwards, a sign that he is guarding the Lodge to prevent any profane or unwelcome persons from entering. This brings us back to the symbolism of Solomon's Temple and the Sephirot, where « Malkuth » (Kingdom) guards the entrance to the Temple facing « Kether » (Crown).

The swords will also be used when the Orator Brother swears his oath of allegiance to the Worshipful Master and the two Wardens of the Lodge.

4. The sword of the Brother Tyler

When the Brother Keeper stands up, he grasps his sword with his right hand and holds it in front of him, pointing upwards. He is the protector of the door to the Temple of the Lodge.

5. The swords of the Brothers

The Brothers use it during the first two journeys of the profane who has left the Cabinet of Reflection. The profane must make three journeys, the last of which is made in silence. According to the ritual, only then can he ask for the light and receive the Light.

When the blindfold is removed from the one who has completed the three journeys that are part of the initiation, the candidate discovers swords pointed at him, which have a double meaning:

- That the brothers are ready to come to his aid
- That the swords are a threat to the brother who has broken his oath

In more detail, the ritual of the modern Belgian rite says the following regarding the three journeys of the profane in the lodge before receiving the Light:

« During the first Journey, you will clash the blades of your swords; during the second Journey, you will slide them against each other as if sharpening them. The third Journey will take place in absolute silence, with only the sound of footsteps to be heard ».

...

« Before giving the Light to the recipient, I will say to you: ‘My Brothers, do your duty!’ You will point the tip of your sword, held in your left hand, towards the recipient. If you do not have a sword, you will point your left index finger towards the recipient. When I say, ‘Lower your swords,’ you will lay down your swords without making a sound ».

The Worshipful Master and the two Wardens, armed with their swords, form a triangle during the knighting of the neophyte:

(The Worshipful Master and the Wardens form a triangle with their swords around the neophyte's neck)

« To the Glory of the Great Architect of the Universe, under the auspices of the Regular Grand Lodge of Belgium and by virtue of the powers vested in me by this Respectable Lodge, regularly assembled at the degree of Apprentice,

YouI create, consecrate, and receive you as an Apprentice Mason..... »

Swords are also used for the reception of the Worshipful Master and high dignitaries such as the Grand Master of the Obedience.

There are also other circumstances in which the Brothers use their swords; for example, in the third degree of Master, when three Master Brothers (then with the participation of the

Worshipful Master, three in total) search for Master Hiram, who has been attacked by three treacherous companions who asked him three times for the secret word of the Master.

Finally, during Masonic celebrations, a ritual is performed at the agape, where swords are used (replaced by knives). This ritual is similar to military banquets. The same type of ritual is used in the modern French rite. These special banquets are also called Table Works or Table Ritual or Ritual Banquet. The vocabulary used is that of military artillery and the gestures are precise, combining order and conviviality. This table ritual is also reminiscent of operative masonry.

While in the 18th century, agape had a strongly epicurean dimension, sometimes with excesses, today, order banquets are more of an initiatory dimension, with values such as sharing food and spirit.

In some Lodges and some rites, swords are present during agapes (table ritual or harmony) and the two solstice celebrations. In some rites, such as the Rectified Scottish Rite, a chivalric rite, each Brother carries a sword during Masonic meetings.

6. History of the appearance of the sword

As far as we know, swords were first produced around 3300 BC, during the Bronze Age. It was in the Middle East that swords seem to have first appeared.

They were made of bronze and were generally about two feet long, equivalent to 24 inches or 60 cm. The sword developed from the knife and dagger, with a sharp edge on both sides of the blade. Already in the Stone Age, men worked stone to make sharp, pointed shapes for hunting or waging war between tribes.

However, the sword gained importance in the Iron Age (a harder metal). The medieval period in Europe was a time when the sword became more sophisticated and widely used for warfare. The sword became a symbol of authority, power, and domination. In the 11th century, the Normans developed the use of hand guards. This practice is also linked to Christian iconography (the Cross of Christ). The swords of the Knights were forged in the shape of a cross. The Crusaders used their swords as crosses while kneeling on the ground.

7. The flaming sword of the Norse gods

Muspelheim was the original world of fire, a dangerous place guarded by a giant named Surtr, guardian of the world, with his flaming sword. Muspelheim was the home of the Fire Giants in Norse religion. This kingdom was known as the « Destroyer of Worlds ». This mythological place was dangerous, generating heat and flames that played a role in the creation of the world, but also in the final destruction of the Universe during Ragnarök (referring to a prophetic end of the world).

Thus, the sword created the Sun, the Moon, and the stars and all light emissions in the Earth's sky. But the sword also represents the death of Freyr, symbolizing peace and fertility.

The sword also contributes to the destruction of Bifrost. Bifröst is the « shimmering path », like a rainbow, a bridge between Earth, called Midgard, and Heaven, called Ásgard. Ásgard was the fortress city of the gods. The story comes from the Poetic Edda, more specifically

from the Voluspa. Sections can also be found in the Prose Edda. It is a story from before the arrival of Christianity in Iceland. Here is an excerpt:

Surtr comes from the south, with the wound of the branches: there, shining with his sword, is the sun of the Gods of the Dead.

8. The flaming sword in ancient Sumer

The god Asaruludu had a « flaming sword », guaranteeing the most perfect security. « It is also the symbolism of “the light of the gods” and the « God who lights our way ». The god Asaruludu is also considered one of the gods who hold « the destiny of man ». Some ancient Sumerian incantation manuscripts refer to this.

Asaruludu or Namshub, one of the Anunnaki associated with magical incantations. The Anunnakis represent a group of deities associated with the divine pantheon. They are the main deities or gods of the underworld according to Sumerian texts.

Ancient Hebrew texts refer to the sword linked to two archangels: Uriel and Jophiel. Both have similar importance in relation to the concepts of « Truth, Wisdom, and Judgement ».

Uriel is the archangel of light, divine wisdom, and prophecy, enabling knowledge and understanding of mysteries. Jophiel is the archangel of beauty and spiritual enlightenment. He is a guide for those seeking inner and outer splendour. Wisdom, knowledge, inner and outer beauty, light with its fire that gives strength and the way forward: these are concepts taken up by Freemasonry.

The Eastern Orthodox Church also speaks of the flaming sword that was placed by the cherubim in the Garden of Eden, but was removed after Christ's resurrection so that humans could once again enter the Kingdom of Heaven.

However, the flaming sword is not part of the Eastern Orthodox liturgy. It is in fact a simple biblical reference in the book of Genesis. The same is true for the Protestant Church, where the flaming sword is a biblical reference.

Its symbolism is linked to the protection of sacred space and access to divine knowledge. This symbolism has been taken up by Freemasonry. However, Knowledge is subject to interpretation depending on Masonic Obediences. For example, in the "Grand Orient de France" (GOF), the concept of Knowledge has no connection with divine Knowledge, whereas for other Obediences, the opposite is true (the "Grande Loge Nationale Française").

9. Esoteric dimension of the sword and the flaming sword

The flaming sword is symbolically linked to the function of guardian of the Temple. Once again, Malkuth, guardians of the Kingdom facing Kether, the Crown, comes to mind. This barrier with the sword indicates that only those who possess Truth or Wisdom may enter sacred places. It is in this sacred place that Truth, which is immeasurable and inexpressible, can be revealed. In the Lodge engaged in spiritual quest, the search for truth allows for the immanence of Truth. The power of this Truth takes the form of a Spirit manifested by fire. The divine symbolize the Truth, and men can benefit from it: that which is above is below,

and that which is below is above. This allows us to have a vision of the Emerald Tablet. This symbolism obviously brings us closer to Freemasonry.

In the light of fire, impurities are burned away so that only what is “real” is perceptible. In Masonic ritual, the Brother at the head of the procession, armed with his sword, shows that he “lights the way of the gods” and perhaps establishes this barrier between the profane and the sacred. The flaming sword creates a sacred space, but also constitutes its destruction. It also reminds us that the Brothers work from noon to midnight (sacred space-time). It also reminds us of the belief of the Nordic tribes regarding creation and destruction.

Swords also generally represent strength and virtue. The sword is a symbol of strength of mind and clarity of reason. The flaming sword, added to the element of “fire,” signifies the spirit overseeing what happens in the macrocosm of which the microcosm is a part.

10. In summary

We can say that the flaming sword is a powerful symbol in Freemasonry, drawing its symbolism from the Bible, but also having symbolic links to the Norse and Sumerian gods. The flaming sword is rich in meaning; it is associated with power, authority, justice, and impartiality.

The flame of the sword evokes purification and enlightenment through the search for light and truth. The flame also symbolizes the power of truth and passion. The flame generates light that burns and illuminates the path of the Mason in his quest. Justice, represented by the sword, allows one to defend a just cause. The flaming sword also symbolizes “protection, deterrence, victory, and divine origin.” Thus, the flaming sword allows for the actualization of the Emerald Tablet: that which is above is below, and vice versa.

11. Poem about the flaming sword

The Flaming Sword

In the hand of man, it sparkles, ardent
The flaming sword, symbol of valour.
Its steel ablaze, like a glowing fire
Illuminates the night, a burst of hope.
It dances in the air, a bright and wild fire
Cutting through shadow and fear, defying fate.
Its radiant glow, like a travelling sun
Warms the brave heart, forging the way.
Beautiful and proud, it sings of freedom,
Eternal flame, the cry of courage.
The flaming sword, symbol of truth
Shines forever, in a world without age.

Sebök Ferenc, 2013

12. The Four Journeys of the Apprentice

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